

MAINSTREAMING EDUCATION PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PALANAN DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the practices and challenges of mainstreaming education for Indigenous learners in secondary schools in the Palanan District of Isabela, Philippines. It focused on the perceptions of administrators, teachers, and students regarding inclusive practices across five key areas: Curriculum Design, Competency and Content; Teaching Methodology and Strategies; Learning Space and Environment; Teaching Resources; and Classroom Assessment. Using a descriptive research design, the study surveyed 453 respondents, including 8 administrators, 139 teachers, and 306 Indigenous students. Findings revealed that teachers consistently practiced inclusive strategies, particularly in curriculum design and classroom environment, although students perceived some areas as less consistently implemented. Significant challenges identified included limited training in inclusive education, insufficient culturally relevant resources, inadequate professional development, and difficulties engaging Indigenous learners due to language and cultural differences. The study also found that demographic factors, such as teacher ethnicity and student grade level, influenced perceptions of teaching practices. While correlations between teachers' practices and challenges were not statistically significant, the study underscores the importance of culturally responsive teaching, institutional support, and collaborative engagement with Indigenous communities to improve educational outcomes and ensure equitable learning opportunities.

Keywords: *Indigenous learners, inclusive education, mainstreaming practices, culturally responsive teaching, secondary schools*

INTRODUCTION

In an ever-evolving educational landscape, the need for inclusive practices that cater to diverse student populations has garnered increased attention, particularly within secondary schools. Mainstream education- integrating students with special educational needs (SEN) into general education settings- presents a transformative approach aimed at fostering equity, promoting social integration and enhancing academic achievement. However, despite the theoretical benefits and the growing momentum towards inclusive education, the practical implementation in secondary schools often reveals a complex interplay of practices and challenges.

Mainstream education should address the needs of all students and eliminate any barriers that may hinder their participation. One significant things is the cultural differences among learners. These differences can lead to poor interpersonal relationships, negatively impacting students' social experiences and possibly causing some to leave school.

Socialization significantly impacts a student's learning, whether in an informal or formal education setting. The sense of belonging encourages students to attend school and engage in reading and writing. Feeling accepted within a group fosters a positive attitude toward learning, as students benefit from the school's welcoming environment. This atmosphere of trust cultivates strong interpersonal relationships and camaraderie among students. With this supportive vision, their physical, mental, and psychological well-being are positively affected.

Mainstreaming provides many of the same benefits as those of an inclusive classroom. Building confidence, better socialization, more challenging academics, and better feelings of belonging and community all happen within the mainstreaming of students.

Including children in mainstream classrooms is a right and not a privilege. Inclusive education ensures high-quality and fair education for all students, including those who are marginalized due to learning disabilities or other special educational needs (UNESCO International Bureau of Education, 2009). Education is a fundamental right that guarantees each child access to a high-quality education serving as a passport for personal development and career readiness. It opens doors to new opportunities, freedoms, and liberties by opening while contributing to the promotion of peace, democracy, economic development, and improvements in health and poverty reduction. Tcheimegni (2018).

Isabela is a province in the Philippines situated in the Cagayan Valley region occupying the northeast section of Luzon. It is composed of thirty-seven (37) municipalities including its four (4) coastal towns of Dinapigue, Divilacan, Maconacon, and Palanan where majority of its inhabitants belongs to diverse Indigenous groups mainly the Dumagat people.

This dissertation sought to explore the teachers' practices of mainstreaming education in secondary institutions in Palanan and challenges that hinder its success as perceived by the administrators, students and teachers themselves. The study focuses on five key areas: Curriculum Design, Competency and Content, Teaching Methodology and Strategies, Learning Space and Environment, Teaching Resources, and Classroom Assessment

Addressing these, not only enriches the discourse surrounding mainstreaming education but also establishes a framework for future research and policy development that prioritizes mainstreaming education.

As a teacher in the coastal town, where most IPs live, mainstreaming education is challenging. Based on experience, IP learners usually drop out due to difficulty of adapting to the learning process in formal education. The languages being used in teaching are not properly understood by students, and acceptance of the culture-related subject is also a problem with their interpersonal relationship with other classmates whom they feel as higher than them.

Buenaflor et.al. (2023), said that Indigenous students often do worse academically than non-indigenous student peers. These stated the low enrollment rates showed a dropout rate, absenteeism, repetition rates, literacy rate, and thus the educational outcomes, with retention and completion being two significant issues. Similarly, the United Nations (2009) stated that IP and nomadic people have faced multiple difficulties in education. Indigenous students often do worse academically than non-indigenous student peers. These stated the low enrollment rates showed a dropout rate, absenteeism, repetition rates, literacy rate, and thus the educational outcomes, with retention and completion being two significant issues.

This scenario is alarming and should be attended to. It is with this premise that the researcher was motivated to look upon the usual mainstream education practices as well as the challenges experienced by those who are teaching IPs in Palanan, Isabela.

Research Questions

This study sought to find out the mainstreaming practices of secondary school teachers of Palanan District and the challenges they encounter. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - a. Administrators
 - a.1 Age
 - a.2 Sex
 - a.3 Position
 - a.4 Years in Teaching
 - a.5 Ethnicity
 - b. Teachers
 - b.1 Age

- b.2 Sex
 - b.3 Position
 - b.4 Years in Teaching
 - b.5 Ethnicity
 - c. Students
 - c.1 Age
 - c.2 Sex
 - c.3 Grade Level
 - c.4 Ethnicity
 - IP _____
2. What are the inclusive practices employed by the teachers in mainstream education in terms of the five key areas as perceived by their administrators, students, and teachers themselves?
 - a. Curriculum Design, Competency and Content
 - b. Teaching Methodology and Strategies
 - c. Learning Space and Environment
 - d. Teaching Resources
 - e. Classroom Assessment
 3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of administrators, students, and teachers themselves on the mainstream education practices of teachers?
 4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the administrators, students, and teachers on mainstream education practices of teachers when grouped according to profile?
 5. To what extent are the challenges experienced by the administrators, the teachers and the students in mainstream education?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the challenges experienced by the teachers in mainstream education as perceived by their administrators, students, and teachers themselves when grouped according to their profile?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' practices and the challenges experienced by the teachers in mainstream education?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive research design. Descriptive research design, as stated by Sirisilla (2023), is a powerful tool used by researchers to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon. This type of research provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject. By observing and collecting data on a given topic, descriptive research helps researchers gain a deeper understanding of a specific issue and provides valuable insights that can inform future studies.

The descriptive design was used in this study to unveil the practices and challenges of teachers in mainstream education.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the four Coastal Towns of the Province of Isabela. It focused on the administrators, teachers and learners in mainstream education focusing on the indigenous learners in the seven secondary schools of Palanan District: Dinapigue National High School, Divilacan National High School, Maconacon National High School and the four secondary schools of Palanan: Dibewan Integrated School, Isabela School of Fisheries, Palanan National High School and Palanan School of Agriculture and Arts for School Year 2024-2025.

Selection and Description of Respondents

A total number of 453 respondents were involved in this study. These includes the total population of eight school heads, 139 teachers and 306 IP learners enrolled in the seven schools of coastal towns in the Division of Isabela for school year 2024-2025. The table presents the distribution of respondents in the study by school.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution of Respondents By School

Name of Schools	School Heads	Total Number of Teachers	Total Number of IP Learners
Dinapigue National High School	1	25	85
Maconacon National High School	1	18	101
Divilacan National High School	1	20	80
Dibewen Integrated School	1	6	0
Isabela School of Fisheries	2	21	10
Palanan National High School	1	31	19
Palanan School of Agriculture and Trades	1	18	11
Sub- Total	8	139	306
TOTAL	453		

This study applied total enumeration sampling. All the school heads, teachers and learners in the mainstream education in the seven schools of Coastal towns in the Division of Isabela who were present during the floating of questionnaires were considered as the respondents.

One secondary school specifically Dibewan Integrated School has no enrolled IP learner in any of its Grade Level for this School Year.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Superintendent and Assistant Superintendent of the Division of Isabela to conduct the study. After approval was granted, the district supervisor and school heads were given a copy of the approved request letter, to allow the teachers teaching mainstreaming indigenous learners and Indigenous People learners to participate in the study. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. After the respondents have answered the questionnaire, the retrieved them and the data gathered were organized and collated.

Statistical Treatment of Data

This study applied the following statistical tools to analyze the gathered data:

Frequency and Percentage Count. This was used to analyze the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, position, and years of teaching.

Weighted Mean. This statistical tool was used to analyze the perception of the respondents on the mainstream education practices, and challenges of teachers.

F- Test. This was employed to find out if there is a significant difference in the perception of the respondents regarding mainstream education practices, and challenges. It was also used to find out if a significant difference exists in the perception of respondents when grouped according to their profile.

Pearson's r-test. This test was employed to determine the relationship between the practices, and challenges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:

A. Administrators

a. Age

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Administrators According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21- 30	1	12.50
31- 40	2	25.00
41- 50	4	50.00
51- 60	1	12.50
TOTAL	8	100

Table 2 shows the age profile of administrators. It reveals that out of eight administrators, 50 percent who belong to the 41-50 age bracket; three are 21 to 40 years old, and one is above 50 years old.

This data implies that half of the number of administrators are in middle adulthood. Studies show that administrators in their 41-50 years of age are generally considered to be in the “peak” phase of their career, characterized by a blend of deep experience, matured wisdom and high productivity. Middle aged administrators in school brings an encouraging environment and manage a career, nurture and expand caring relationships. They also integrate the skills and perspectives of earlier life stages with a commitment of energy for the future. DaiKiYa. (2024).

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Administrators According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	5	62.50
Female	3	37.50
TOTAL	8	100

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of administrators according to sex. It reveals that majority or 62.50 percent are male and 37.50 percent are female.

The sex distribution of administrators shows a higher proportion of males compared to females. According to Sstumurray.com, masculine qualities of leadership include having a clear vision, being assertive, and leading with integrity. These traits involve setting a direction for oneself and the team, expressing needs and desires confidently, and taking accountability for actions Murray (2024).

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Administrators According to Position

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher-In-Charge	2	25.00
Head Teacher-III	3	37.50
Principal I	1	12.50
Principal II	2	25.00
TOTAL	8	

Table 4 present the position held by administrators. Based on the table , 37.50% are head teachers, 25% are Teacher-in-charge and three hold a Principal position.

The result shows the slim chances of becoming Principal due to the Qualification Standards demanded by the position, that one should be a passer first of the NQESH before joining the assessment for the principal position.

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Administrators According to Years in Service

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	1	12.50
6-10	1	12.50
11-15	2	25.00
16-20	2	25.00
21-25	2	25.00
26-30	-	-
30 Years & Above	-	-
TOTAL	8	100

Table 5 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of administrators according to years in service. The data reveals that 50 % have served for 16 years or more. This means that half of the administrator respondents are experienced in their work as school heads.

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Administrators According to Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
IP	3	37.50
NON-IP	5	62.50
TOTAL	8	100

The frequency and percentage distribution of the administrators according to ethnicity. The table shows that majority or 62.50 % are non-indigenous.

In an interview with the non-indigenous administrators, they face some challenges in catering to indigenous students in the school. Thus, they usually attend specific training and cultural sensitivity to effectively serve in their school environment.

B. Teachers

a. Age

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	46	33.09
31-40	50	35.97

41-50	32	23.02
51-60	9	6.48
61 and above	2	1.44
TOTAL	139	100

Table 7 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the age profile of teachers.

Majority of the teachers are aged 21 to 40 years old. This shows that majority of the respondents are in their early adulthood. According to Developmental Psychology early adulthood is a period of significant transition and exploration. During this time, many adults focus on personal development, building relationships, establishing careers, and pursuing long-term goals.

b. Sex

Table 8
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	44	31.65
Female	95	68.34
TOTAL	139	100

Table 8 discloses the frequency and percentage distribution of teachers according to sex. The table shows 68.34% are female and 31.65% are male.

This confirms the common observation that in many places there are more female in the teaching workforce. In Palanan, there are more females pursuing higher education, particularly in teaching-related field than man, leading to a larger female teacher workforce. Research shows that the dominance of female teachers in the Philippines, particularly in basic education, is “rooted in deeply ingrained gender stereotype that associate teaching -especially nurturing younger children- with women’s inherent maternal roles”.

c. Position

Table 9
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers According to Position

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	47	33.81
Teacher II	18	12.94
Teacher III	69	49.64
Master Teacher I	4	2.87
Master Teacher II	1	0.71
TOTAL	139	100

Table 9 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of teachers according to position. Data shows that most of the teachers hold a Teacher III position and a few hold a Master Teacher position.

Teacher III position is typically given to educators with more experience, higher qualifications, and possibly specialized skills. Schools with more Teacher III suggest a strong foundation of seasoned teachers. There are only five Master Teachers because of the rigid criteria for promotion. It needs to consider the supervisory and technical assistance to the teachers and only few teachers are promoted to this Plantilla.

Table 10
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers According to Years in Service

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	52	37.41
6-10	41	29.49
11-15	22	15.82
16-20	10	7.19
21-25	3	2.15
26-30	4	2.87
31 years and above	7	5.03
TOTAL	139	100

Table 10 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher respondents based on their years of service. The findings show that majority or about 67% of the teachers have been in the service for 1 to 10 years. The remaining 33% have served for more than 10 years.

This implies that most of the respondents are young in the service. A higher number of new teachers means that the school system is expanding, hiring fresh educators to accommodate rising student populations or new schools.

d. Ethnicity

Table 11
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers According to Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
IP	41	29.50
Ilocano	2	4.87
Kalinga	2	4.87
Kankanaey	1	2.43
Paranan	15	36.58
Tinguian	2	4.87
Ybanag	18	43.90
Yogad	1	2.43
NON-IP	98	70.50
TOTAL	139	100

The table presents the distribution of teacher-respondents according to their ethnicity. The data reveals that a great majority of the teachers are non-IP and a 30.5% are IPs. The teachers who belong to IP are mostly Ybanags and Paranan.

C. Students
a. Age

Table 12
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
11-13	79	25.82
14-16	164	53.59
17-19	63	20.59
TOTAL	306	100

Table 12 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of student-respondents according to age. Majority belong to age bracket of 14-16 years, 25.82% are 11-13 years old and 20.59% belong to 17-19 years age bracket.

This indicates that a significant portion of the student body is in the middle of their teenage years, a crucial development age. Coral Care (2025) say that this stage is characterized by intense peer focus, a drive for independence from parents and rapid cognitive growth toward abstract thinking.

b. Sex

Table 13
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	140	45.75
Female	166	54.25
TOTAL	306	100

Table 13 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students according to sex. Based on the table, there are 166 or 54.25 female and 140 or 45.75% male.

It implies that there is almost equal distribution of students according to sex. As observed by the researcher in, girls may have greater access to education compared to boys, leading to higher enrollment rates.

c. Grade Level

Table 14
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students According to Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
7	71	23.20

8	40	13.07
9	73	23.85
10	52	16.99
11	52	16.99
12	18	5.88
TOTAL	306	100

The table above presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students according to grade level. The data shows that Grades 7 and 9 have the most number of students and Grade 12 has the least.

It is very alarming to note that of 306 high school students, only 18 reach grade 12. As experienced by the researcher, many students tend to leave school before completing their secondary education.

d. Ethnicity

Table 15
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students According to Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
IP	306	100
Agta	48	15.68
Bolinaw	1	0.32
Dupaninan-Agta	16	5.22
Ifugaw	15	4.90
Igorot	48	15.68
Ilocano	1	0.32
Itawes	2	0.65
Itneg	53	17.32
Kalinga	23	7.51
Kankanaey	4	1.30
Manobo	10	3.26
Muslim	1	0.32
Pangasinense	2	0.65
Paranan	50	16.33
Tagalog	2	0.65
Tinguian	4	1.30
Waray	3	0.98
Ybanag	21	6.86
Yogad	2	0.65
TOTAL	306	100

Table 15 shows that all students belong to an ethnic group. It also reveals that the biggest group are the Itneg students followed by the Paranan, Igorot and Agta. Furthermore, data shows that the students in Palanan is a mixture of different ethnic groups.

2. What are the inclusive practices employed by the teachers in mainstream education in terms of the five key areas as perceived by their administrators, students, and teachers themselves?

**Table 16
Inclusive Practices Employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education As Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Curriculum Design, Competency and Content**

Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	Administrators		Teachers		Students	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Create learning objectives that align with curriculum standards.	3.37	Always Practiced	3.84	Always Practiced	3.22	Frequently Practiced
2. Incorporate feedback from stakeholders (e.g. students, parents, colleagues) into my curriculum design.	3.50	Always Practiced	3.59	Always Practiced	3.00	Frequently Practiced
3. Integrating technology into my curriculum design.	3.25	Always Practiced	3.65	Always Practiced	2.94	Frequently Practiced
4. Include diverse perspective and inclusiveness in my lessons.	3.25	Always Practiced	3.62	Always Practiced	3.17	Frequently Practiced
5. Lessons are relevant to the content of today's social, cultural, and economic contexts.	3.50	Always Practiced	3.73	Always Practiced	3.26	Always Practiced
6. Rate the quality of assessments used to measure student understanding of the curriculum.	3.37	Always Practiced	3.65	Always Practiced	3.19	Frequently Practiced
7. Contextualize the curriculum based on assessment data and student feedback.	2.87	Frequently Practiced	3.50	Always Practiced	3.09	Frequently Practiced
8. Attend professional development opportunities to pursue contextualization of curriculum.	2.87	Frequently Practiced	3.47	Always Practiced	3.09	Frequently Practiced
9. Involved with other educators in collaborative curriculum design efforts.	3.12	Frequently Practiced	3.34	Always Practiced	2.96	Frequently Practiced
10. Support what is necessary for improving curriculum design in my class.	3.37	Always Practiced	3.73	Always Practiced	3.26	Always Practiced
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.25	Always Practiced	3.61	Always Practiced	3.11	Frequently Practiced

Table 16 presents the inclusive practices employed by the teachers in Mainstream Education as perceived by the respondents in terms of Curriculum Design, Competency and Content.

Teachers always support what is necessary for improving curriculum design in their class, and always see to it that lessons are relevant to the content of today's social, cultural, and economic contexts as perceived by the administrators, students and teachers themselves. The administrators and teachers themselves claim that creating learning objectives that align with curriculum standards, incorporating feedback from stakeholders (e.g. students, parents, colleagues) into the curriculum design, integrating technology into their curriculum design, and including diverse perspective and inclusiveness in their lessons are always practiced by the teachers while the students claim that these are frequently practiced. The teachers perceived that they always practiced contextualizing the curriculum based on assessment data and student feedback, attending professional development opportunities to pursue contextualization of curriculum, and working with other educators in collaborative curriculum design efforts while the administrators and the students perceive these to be frequently practiced.

In a study conducted by Akintayo, et.al. (2024) on inclusive education, he specified that inclusive curriculum design is a critical framework in contemporary education aimed at addressing the diverse needs of students for fostering social improvement. Moreover, inclusive curriculum design promotes the incorporation of culturally responsive teaching practices that validate students' identities and experiences. By integrating diverse perspectives into the curriculum, educators can foster empathy, understanding, and respect among students, contributing to a more inclusive and harmonious society. The study of Verdida (2024) to determine the lived experiences of IPED teachers in integrating the IPED curriculum stated that to cope with the mentioned challenges, IPED teachers had to seek assistance from I.P. leaders in the community, attend IPed seminars and workshops, and observe flexibility and open-mindedness.

Table 17
Inclusive Practices Employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education As Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Teaching Methodology and Strategies

Teaching Methodology and Strategies	Administrators		Teachers		Students	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Implements the Indigenous Peoples Education Framework.	3.00	Frequently Practiced	3.34	Always Practiced	3.26	Always Practiced
2. Integrates indigenous knowledge and perspectives into teaching methods.	3.13	Frequently Practiced	3.45	Always Practiced	3.16	Frequently Practiced
3. Uses teaching methods to incorporate indigenous perspectives.	3.25	Always Practiced	3.39	Always Practiced	3.11	Frequently Practiced
4. Uses culturally relevant materials and resources in teaching.	3.38	Always Practiced	3.44	Always Practiced	3.09	Frequently Practiced
5. Employs Indigenous teaching methods (e.g., storytelling, land-based education)	3.13	Frequently Practiced	3.32	Always Practiced	3.07	Frequently Practiced
6. Encourages students to be participative in the different	3.25	Always Practiced	3.58	Always Practiced	3.18	Frequently Practiced

indigenous teaching methods used in the classroom.						
7. Includes indigenous teaching methods to promote a deeper understanding of cultural diversity among students.	3.13	Frequently Practiced	3.52	Always Practiced	3.10	Frequently Practiced
8. Collaborates with indigenous community members or leaders in teaching.	2.75	Frequently Practiced	3.11	Frequently Practiced	3.08	Frequently Practiced
9. Values the importance of community involvement in the effectiveness of IP education.	3.50	Frequently Practiced	3.69	Always Practiced	3.23	Frequently Practiced
10. Requests resources or support that would help in the implementation of indigenous teaching methods.	2.63	Frequently Practiced	3.23	Frequently Practiced	3.05	Frequently Practiced
TOTAL	3.11	Frequently Practice	3.40	Always Practice	3.13	Frequently Practice

Table 17 presents the teaching methodology and strategies employed by the teachers in mainstream education as perceived by the administrators, teachers and students. The administrators, teachers and students were one in their perception that teachers **frequently** collaborate with indigenous community members or leaders in teaching and request resources or support that would help in the implementation of indigenous teaching methods. On the other hand, the administrators and teachers perceived that using teaching methods to incorporate indigenous perspectives, using culturally relevant materials and resources in teaching, and encouraging students to be participative in the different indigenous teaching methods used in the classroom are **always practiced** by the teachers while the students perceive these to be **frequently practiced**. The teachers claim that they **always practiced** the integration of indigenous knowledge and perspectives into teaching methods, employment of indigenous teaching methods (e.g., storytelling, land-based education to promote a deeper understanding of cultural diversity among students, and value the importance of community involvement in the effectiveness of IP education while the administrators and students perceived these to be frequently practiced. Moreover, the implementation of the Indigenous Peoples Education Framework is perceived by the teachers and students to be **always practiced** while the administrators say these is **frequently** done.

Teachers claim that they always do their best in serving learners specifically in teaching strategies. They have elaborate discussions to meet the needs of the learners. Some teachers even mentioned during interviews that they do research and spend sleepless nights to prepare their lessons. Despite this effort done by the teachers, some students claim that they are having difficulties comprehending the lesson because they cannot grasp the teaching method. It is beyond their capability to absorb. This is the reason why there is a need for the school, especially teachers, to collaborate with the IP community and leaders to properly know how to impart, approach and know the existing differences for the IP learners.

The role of the IP leaders in education was revealed in the basic qualitative study of Basiwal-Ao-wat and Ayang-ang (2024) which delved into the pivotal role of Indigenous Peoples (IP) leaders in the indigenization of the curriculum, acting as the cornerstone for the development of an Indigenous Peoples Education Program. The study investigated the multifaceted responsibilities undertaken by IP leaders, assuming roles such as translators, facilitators/ resource persons, coordinators, and narrators in the intricate process of curriculum development.

Table 18
Inclusive Practices Employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Learning Space and Environment

Learning Space and Environment	Administrators		Teachers		Students	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Create learning spaces that respect indigenous perspectives and cultures.	3.25	Always Practice	3.59	Always Practice	3.35	Always Practice
2. Utilize outdoor or land-based learning spaces in teaching.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.26	Always Practice	3.00	Frequently Practice
3. Assess the physical learning environments (classrooms, libraries, outdoor spaces) in the school to reflect and respect indigenous cultures and traditions.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.37	Always Practice	3.16	Frequently Practice
4. Evaluate the availability and accessibility of a culturally relevant atmosphere in the learning environment.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.40	Always Practice	3.10	Frequently Practice
5. Design a learning environment that impacts student engagement with indigenous knowledge and practices.	3.25	Always Practice	3.44	Always Practice	3.12	Frequently Practice
6. Provide opportunities for learners to be comfortable in discussing about indigenous cultures in the classroom.	3.50	Frequently Practice	3.63	Always Practice	3.20	Frequently Practice
7. Include Indigenous community members in the planning and use of learning spaces,	3.00	Frequently Practice	3.28	Always Practice	3.11	Frequently Practice
8. Incorporate pictures of indigenous cultural practices (e.g., beliefs, traditional ceremonies during weddings, and death rituals) in a particular space provided in a classroom.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.40	Always Practice	3.09	Frequently Practice

9. Address challenges encountered in creating or utilizing indigenous-friendly learning spaces.	3.25	Always Practice	3.41	Always Practice	3.12	Frequently Practice
10. Determine the kind of classroom or support that would help improve the learning environment aligned with Indigenous education principles.	3.25	Always Practice	3.37	Always Practice	3.21	Frequently Practice
TOTAL	3.20	Frequently Practice	3.41	Always Practice	3.14	Frequently Practice

The table shows that create learning spaces that respect indigenous perspectives and cultures is **always practiced** by the teachers as perceived by the three groups of respondents. The administrators and teachers claim that designing a learning environment that impacts student engagement with indigenous knowledge and practices, addressing challenges encountered in creating or utilizing indigenous-friendly learning spaces, and determining the kind of classroom or support that would help improve the learning environment aligned with Indigenous education principles are **always practiced** by the teachers while the students say these are **frequently practiced**. The teachers, on the other hand, say that they **always** utilize outdoor or land-based learning spaces in teaching, assess the physical learning environments (classrooms, libraries, outdoor spaces) in the school to reflect and respect indigenous cultures and traditions, evaluate the availability and accessibility of a culturally relevant atmosphere in the learning environment, provide opportunities for learners to be comfortable in discussing about indigenous cultures in the classroom, include Indigenous community members in the planning and use of learning spaces, and incorporate pictures of indigenous cultural practices (e.g., beliefs, traditional ceremonies during weddings, and death rituals) in a particular space provided in a classroom. However, the administrators and students perceive these to be frequently practiced.

The teachers tend to believe that they always practice learning space and environment in the mainstream education, but the administrators and students disclosed that the teachers frequently practice this in inclusive education. Furthermore, the inclusion of indigenous community members in the planning and the use of learning spaces and utilize outdoor or land-based learning spaces in teaching got the lowest mean from the administrators and students.

This implies that the teachers should include the IPs and community members in planning and apply outdoor learnings. But teachers stated during interview that they have difficulties also explaining things to the IP leaders and will always agree on what the decision of the school will be. Moreover, if they schedule orientation or parent meetings, seldom do the IP parents attend. By chance that there is home visitation, they just agree on whatever the teacher says or decides. There are no queries being raised. These difficulties experienced by the teachers handling inclusive education is one of the most challenging -the awareness and participation of the IPs towards school-based decision making.

Table 19
Inclusive Practices Employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education as Perceived by the Respondents in terms of Teaching Resources

Learning Resources	Administrators		Teachers		Students	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Utilizes culturally relevant resources in teaching Indigenous perspectives.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.38	Always Practice	3.22	Frequently Practice
2. Identifies the types of learning resources to be used in teaching indigenous perspectives.	3.0	Frequently Practice	3.35	Always Practice	3.13	Frequently Practice
3. Considers the availability of culturally relevant learning resources in the school.	3.0	Frequently Practice	3.49	Always Practice	3.18	Frequently Practice
4. Incorporates indigenous learning resources into the lesson plans.	2.88	Frequently Practice	3.33	Always Practice	3.07	Frequently Practice
5. Assesses the effectiveness of available resources in enhancing students' understanding of indigenous cultures and perspectives.	3.0	Frequently Practice	3.34	Always Practice	3.09	Frequently Practice
6. Fosters a more inclusive learning resource in the classroom environment.	3.38	Always Practice	3.55	Always Practice	3.18	Frequently Practice
7. Attends training or professional development focused on using indigenous learning resources.	2.75	Frequently Practice	3.01	Frequently Practice	3.08	Frequently Practice
8. Finds it significant to apply what are the learnings in training regarding the use of such resources.	2.88	Frequently Practice	3.26	Always Practice	3.06	Frequently Practice
9. Believes that there is a need for additional support to better utilize indigenous learning resources in the classroom.	3.38	Always Practice	2.94	Frequently Practice	3.17	Frequently Practice
10. Faces challenges in integrating indigenous learning resources into teaching.	3.0	Frequently Practice	3.51	Always Practice	3.06	Frequently Practice
TOTAL	3.04	Frequently Practice	3.31	Always Practice	3.12	Frequently Practice

Table 19 displays the inclusive practices of the teachers in terms of learning resources. The administrators and students claim that the teachers frequently practiced utilizing culturally relevant resources in teaching Indigenous perspectives, identifying the types of learning resources to be used in teaching indigenous perspectives, considering the availability of culturally relevant learning resources in the school, incorporating indigenous learning resources into the lesson plans, and assessing the effectiveness of available resources in enhancing students' understanding of indigenous cultures and

perspectives. However, the teachers say that they ***always practiced*** them. Fostering a more inclusive learning resource in the classroom environment is ***always practiced*** by the teachers according to them and the administrators while the students say this is ***frequently practiced***. The three groups of respondents were one in saying that the teachers ***frequently*** attend training or professional development focused on using indigenous learning resources. According to the administrators, the teachers always believe that there is a need for additional support to better utilize indigenous learning resources in the classroom but the teachers and students believe otherwise.

Table 20
Inclusive Practices employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education as perceived by the Respondents in terms of Classroom Assessment

Classroom Assessment	Administrators		Teachers		Students	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Believes in the importance of assessment in understanding indigenous perspectives and knowledge among students.	3.5	Frequently Practice	3.57	Always Practice	3.30	Frequently Practice
2. Determines type of assessments methods to use in evaluating students understanding of indigenous perspectives.	3.30	Always Practice	3.40	Always Practice	3.16	Frequently Practice
3. Incorporates indigenous knowledge and perspectives in assessments.	3.25	Always Practice	3.37	Always Practice	3.08	Frequently Practice
4. Uses criteria to assess students understanding of indigenous knowledge.	2.88	Frequently Practice	3.34	Always Practice	3.06	Frequently Practice
5. Makes sure that assessment practices are capturing students understanding of indigenous perspectives.	3.25	Always Practice	3.35	Always Practice	3.22	Frequently Practice
6. Helps promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of indigenous cultures among students.	3.38	Always Practice	3.45	Always Practice	3.12	Frequently Practice
7. Attends training on culturally responsive assessment practices related to indigenous education.	2.63	Frequently Practice	2.86	Frequently Practice	3.03	Frequently Practice
8. Considers the trainings very useful in enhancing assessment practices.	2.88	Frequently Practice	3.25	Always Practice	3.12	Frequently Practice
9. Identifies types of resources or support that would help improve assessment practices in	2.88	Frequently Practice	3.29	Always Practice	3.22	Frequently Practice

relation to indigenous education.						
10. Addresses challenges encountered when assessing students understanding of indigenous perspectives.	3.13	Frequently Practice	3.32	Always Practice	3.15	Frequently Practice
TOTAL	3.10	Frequently Practice	3.32	Always Practice	3.15	Frequently Practice

Table 20 reveals the practices employed by the teachers in classroom assessment. The administrators disclosed that the teachers always believe in the importance of assessment in understanding indigenous perspectives and knowledge among students and help promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of indigenous cultures among students. On one hand, the following are frequently practiced by the teachers as perceived by the administrators: identifying types of resources or support that would help improve assessment practices in relation to indigenous education and attending training on culturally responsive assessment practices related to indigenous education.

For the teachers, they believe that they **always** employ the importance of assessment in understanding indigenous perspectives and knowledge among students and help promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of indigenous cultures among students and they **frequently** attend training on culturally responsive assessment practices related to indigenous education.

As for the student's perception, they claim that teachers **always** believe in the importance of assessment in understanding indigenous perspectives and knowledge among students while the incorporating indigenous knowledge and perspectives in assessments, using criteria to assess students understanding of indigenous knowledge, and attend training on culturally responsive assessment practices related to indigenous education are **frequently practiced**.

The perception of attending training on culturally responsive assessment practices related to indigenous education was synonymously perceived by the respondents as frequently practiced by the three respondents. Obviously, training and seminars are important to upgrade and enhance the methods of the teacher's classroom assessment aside from their career growth. Most of the teachers are also non-IPs which will greatly affect the inclusive practices. As such, the mainstream educators need to increase their cultural awareness to properly understand the rights of IPs, and this will only be addressed if they attend seminars with related topics.

Accordingly, professional development is a part of every teacher's career. When professional development is done well, it provides an opportunity for teachers to grow their knowledge and sharpen their skills, which can lead to better student outcomes. It is a way for teachers to collaborate with their colleagues, and there is one avenue through which administrators can support their teachers Schwartz (2023).

Table 21
Summary of Inclusive Practices Employed by the Teachers in Mainstream Education

PRACTICES	Mean	Qualitative Description
Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	3.49	Always Practiced
Teaching Methodology and Strategies	3.38	Always Practiced
Learning Space and Environment	3.42	Always Practiced
Teaching Resources	3.32	Always Practice
Classroom Assessment	3.35	Always Practice

Table 21 shows the summary of the practices of teachers in main streaming. Data shows that the respondents **always practice** the five indicators. The respondents focus more on the curriculum design, competency and content with a mean of 3.49, followed by learning space and environment with a mean of 3.42, teaching methodology and strategies with a mean of 3.38, classroom assessment, 3.35 and teaching resources, 3.32. This implies that the teachers as perceived by them, the administrators and the students always employ the inclusive practices for the good of the learners. It proves further that the teachers teach in alignment with the curriculum designed by the DepEd to meet the needed competencies. Moreover, although the teachers employ this practices, they still need more and enhanced resources to meet the learning gaps. Some teachers in one school disclosed that *“in as much as we want to add and request more learning resources, the school has insufficient budget”*. Hence, the teachers make ways to cater to the need like printing what they search on the internet connected with the competencies being develop and work collaboratively with their co-teachers.

3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the administrators, students, and teachers themselves on the inclusive education practices employed by the teachers?

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of Administrators, Students and Teachers Themselves on Inclusive Education Practices of Teachers

Mainstream Education Practices in the following key areas	Mean			P - value	Analysis	Remarks
	Admin	Teachers	Students			
Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	3.25	3.61	3.12	P < 0.001	P<0.05	Significant
Teaching Methodology and Strategies	3.12	3.41	3.13	P = 0.002	P<0.05	Significant
Learning Space and Environment	3.20	3.42	3.15	P < 0.001	P<0.05	Significant
Teaching Resources	3.04	3.32	3.12	P = 0.004	P<0.05	Significant
Classroom Assessment	3.11	3.32	3.15	P = 0.054	P>0.05	Not significant

Table 22 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perceptions of administrators, teachers, and students on the teachers' mainstream education practices across five key areas: Curriculum Design, Competency and Content, Teaching Methodology and Practices, Learning Space and Environment; Teaching Resources, and Classroom Assessment.

The results show that the p-values for Curriculum Design, Competency and Content, Teaching Methodology and Practices, Learning Space and Environment, and Teaching Resources are less than the 0.05 level of significance, hence the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the teachers' practices along the areas mentioned significantly vary. Notably, teachers consistently rated the key areas slightly higher than administrators and students, as reflected in the mean scores. This may be attributed to their direct involvement in instructional delivery, curriculum implementation, and the utilization of educational resources.

On the other hand, the area of Classroom Assessment yielded a p-value of 0.054, greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in perceptions of the three groups along this area. This suggests that there is a shared or common understanding among administrators, teachers, and students about how assessment is carried out in classrooms, pointing to a level of alignment in this specific area of practice.

The result shows that administrators prioritize classroom organization and safety, while students may value a supportive and stimulating environment that facilitates learning and social interaction.

Langelan (2024) emphasized that teachers may see their classroom as a reflection of their teaching philosophy and strive to create a positive learning environment. Administrators may emphasize resource availability and alignment with the curriculum, while students may value the relevance and quality of materials used in instruction. According to Munna and Kalam (2021), teachers utilize a variety of resources, from traditional textbooks to technology and real-world examples. Administrators may focus on standardized testing and accountability measures, while students may value feedback and opportunities to demonstrate their learning in multiple ways. Additionally, Onyishi and Sefhoto (2020) stated that teachers may use a range of assessment methods, from traditional tests to performance-based assessments, to gauge student understanding.

4. Is there a significant difference in the mainstream education practices of teachers as perceived by their administrators, teachers and students themselves when grouped according to profile?

a. Administrators

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Mainstream Education Practices of Teachers as Perceived by the Administrators When Grouped According to their Profile

Mainstream Education Practices in the following key areas	Profile	P-value	Analysis	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	Age	0.182	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.082	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.305	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.322	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.601	P > 0.05	Not significant
Teaching Methodology and Strategies	Age	0.222	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.186	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.734	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.233	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.555	P > 0.05	Not significant
Learning Space and Environment	Age	0.289	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.117	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.366	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.396	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.711	P > 0.05	Not significant
Teaching Resources	Age	0.342	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.489	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.475	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.339	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.524	P > 0.05	Not significant
Classroom Assessment	Age	0.543	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.068	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.378	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.557	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.546	P > 0.05	Not significant

Table 23 shows the results of the test of significant difference in the mainstream education practices of teachers as perceived by the administrators when grouped according to age, sex, position, years in service, and ethnicity profiles.

The results reveal p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance for all profile variables across the different areas of mainstream education practices—namely Curriculum Design, Competency and Content; Teaching Methodology and Strategies; Learning Space and Environment; Teaching Resources; and Classroom Assessment. This indicates that administrators' perception of the mainstream education practices of teachers do not significantly differs when grouped according to their age, sex, position, years in service, and ethnicity. The findings suggest that administrators have a generally consistent view of teachers' practices, regardless of their demographic or professional backgrounds. This may imply that mainstream educational practices are uniformly implemented across different groups, or that administrators apply a standard set of criteria when evaluating teaching practices.

b. Teachers

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Mainstream Education Practices of Teachers as Perceived by Them When Grouped According to Their Profile

Mainstream Education Practices in the following key areas	Profile	P-value	Analysis	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	Age	0.613	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.465	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.516	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.539	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.019	P < 0.05	significant
Teaching Methodology and Strategies	Age	0.918	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.425	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.727	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.342	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.145	P > 0.05	Not significant
Learning Space and Environment	Age	0.724	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.377	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.974	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.995	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.357	P > 0.05	Not significant
Teaching Resources	Age	0.892	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.152	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.879	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.806	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.360	P > 0.05	Not significant
Classroom Assessment	Age	0.867	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Sex	0.434	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Years in service	0.693	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Position	0.749	P > 0.05	Not significant
	Ethnicity	0.029	P < 0.05	significant

Table 24 reveals the results of the test of significant difference in the mainstream education practices of the teachers as perceived by them when grouped according to their age, sex, years in service, position, and ethnicity.

The results show that the p - value for the profile *ethnicity* is less than the 0.05 level of significance in the area of curriculum design and classroom assessment. This leads to the rejection of the null hypotheses in these two areas. Thus, there is a significant difference in the teachers' mainstream education practices in Curriculum Design, Competency and Content and Classroom Assessment when grouped according to ethnicity. This implies that ethnic background influence how teachers perceive or implement curriculum content and assessment strategies. Teachers from different ethnic groups may have diverse cultural perspectives and educational experiences which may

shape their interpretation of curriculum relevance, content delivery, and assessment methods.

On the other hand, the p-values for the profile variables **age**, **sex**, **years in service**, and **position** are greater than the 0.05 significance level in four areas. As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that regardless of their age, sex, years in service, and position, teachers tend to have common practices in curriculum design and classroom assessment, teaching methodology and strategies, learning space and environment, and teaching resources.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers' ethnic backgrounds may affect how they view certain areas, like curriculum and assessment. However, in most areas of teaching practice, teachers share similar views. This shows that schools may have a strong, consistent approach to teaching, but it also points to the importance of making curriculum and assessment more culturally responsive.

c. Students

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Students' Perception of the Mainstream Education Practices of Teachers When Grouped According to their Profile

Mainstream Education Practices in the following key areas	Profile	P-value	Analysis	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competency and Content	Age	0.170	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
	Sex	0.133	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
	Grade level	0.026	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Ethnicity	0.032	$P < 0.05$	significant
Teaching Methodology and Strategies	Age	0.028	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Sex	0.026	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Grade level	< 0.001	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Ethnicity	0.022	$P < 0.05$	significant
Learning Space and Environment	Age	0.238	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
	Sex	0.017	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Grade level	0.004	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Ethnicity	0.052	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
Teaching Resources	Age	0.261	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
	Sex	0.001	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Grade level	0.005	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Ethnicity	0.023	$P < 0.05$	significant
Classroom Assessment	Age	0.122	$P > 0.05$	Not significant
	Sex	0.001	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Grade level	0.032	$P < 0.05$	significant
	Ethnicity	0.026	$P < 0.05$	significant

Table 25 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the mainstream education practices of teachers as perceived by students when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that students' perceptions on the teaching methodology and strategies of teachers significantly differ when grouped according to age. When grouped according to grade level, students' significantly vary in their perception of the teachers' practices in terms of curriculum design, competency and content; teaching methodology and strategies; learning space and environment; teaching resources and classroom assessment. Students' ethnicity causes significant difference in the students' perception of the teachers practices along curriculum design, competency and content; teaching methodology and strategies; teaching resources and classroom assessment. When grouped according to sex, the students' perceptions of the teachers' practices on teaching methodology, learning space and environment, teaching resources and classroom assessment.

These results suggest that student demographic profile, particularly sex, age, grade level, and ethnicity, play a critical role in shaping how they perceive the teaching practices implemented in mainstream education settings.

5. To what extent are the challenges experienced by administrators, teachers and students in mainstream education?

a. Administrators

**Table 26
Challenges Experienced by Administrators in Mainstream Education**

Challenges	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Encouraging the incorporation of indigenous culture and history in the curriculum.	3.25	Very Challenging
2. Examining the use of culturally relevant teaching materials and resources.	3.13	Moderately Challenging
3. Strengthening engagement with local indigenous communities in curriculum development.	2.75	Moderately Challenging
4. Monitoring the implementation of differentiated instruction tailored to the needs of IP learners.	2.75	Moderately Challenging
5. Encouraging the integration of indigenous languages in the learning process.	2.63	Moderately Challenging
6. Providing training on culturally responsive teaching practices for IP learners.	3.13	Moderately Challenging
7. Allocating budget for the professional development programs for teachers on IPed.	2.75	Moderately Challenging
8. Addressing the challenges encountered in implementing the IPed curriculum framework for IP learners.	2.75	Moderately Challenging
9. Investigating the extent of socio-economic factors that affect the educational experience of IP learners in school.	3.13	Moderately Challenging
10. Examining specific support of resources as deemed necessary to address challenges of implementing IPed.	2.88	Moderately Challenging

11. Assessing the academic performance of IP learners in the school compared to non-IP learners.	2.88	Moderately Challenging
12. Monitoring the current curriculum framework that might support the socio-emotional well-being of IP learners.	2.50	Moderately Challenging
13. Monitoring the availability of learning resources (textbooks etc.) for IP learners.	2.75	Moderately Challenging
14. Approving extra-curricular activities intended for IP learners' participation.	2.25	Moderately Challenging
15. Conducting program implementation review for project proponents of teachers assigned for IP related programs.	2.50	Moderately Challenging
TOTAL	2.86	Moderately Challenging

Table 26 presents the challenges experienced by the administrators. The table shows that encouraging the incorporation of indigenous culture and history in the curriculum is very challenging for the teachers. Monitoring the current curriculum framework that might support the socio-emotional well-being of IP learners, approving extra-curricular activities intended for IP learners' participation, examining the use of culturally relevant teaching materials and resources, encouraging the integration of indigenous languages in the learning process, providing training on culturally responsive teaching practices for IP learners, allocating budget for the professional development programs for teachers on IPed, addressing the challenges encountered in implementing the IPed curriculum framework for IP learners, examining specific support of resources as deemed necessary to address challenges of implementing IPed, assessing the academic performance of IP learners in the school compared to non-IP learners, monitoring the current curriculum framework that might support the socio-emotional well-being of IP learners, monitoring the availability of learning resources (textbooks etc.) for IP learners, approving extra-curricular activities intended for IP learners' participation are moderately challenging according to the administrators.

Administrators consider the incorporation of indigenous culture and history in the curriculum as very challenging because teachers may lack the necessary knowledge and skills to teach indigenous content effectively, leading to inaccurate or insensitive representations. It's crucial to ensure that indigenous knowledge is presented accurately and respectfully, searching appropriate resources, including materials written in indigenous languages and perspectives, can be difficult. Also, for some teachers, they resist the incorporation of indigenous content due to a lack of understanding or a belief that it is not relevant to the broader curriculum.

As stated in an IP Conference by Alangui (2024), the principal factors or elements in IP Education are the following: a curriculum that is based on the ancestral domain (taken here to mean not only the physical environment but also includes spiritual, cultural, and traditional practices). In other words, the curriculum should be able to address and incorporate special needs, histories, identities, languages, knowledge, and other aspects of their culture, as well as their social economic and cultural priorities and aspirations (D.O. 62).

In addition, teachers have deep consciousness and understanding of the people's and community's culture and aspirations, active involvement of knowledge holders/cultural bearers/elders in the learning process and in curriculum development and teachers and knowledge holders engage in the production and revision of instructional materials.

b. Teachers

Table 27
Challenges Experienced by Teachers in Mainstream Education

Challenges	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. There is a lack of training which affects my ability to teach IP topics.	3.41	Very Challenging
2. There are inadequate resources (texts, materials, etc.) that affect the teaching-learning process of IP education effectively.	3.36	Very Challenging
3. Diverse students' needs are difficult to meet.	3.24	Moderately Challenging
4. There is no sufficient time for lesson planning to integrate IPed.	3.14	Moderately Challenging
5. There is a lack of administrative support in implementing IP education.	3.05	Moderately Challenging
6. Opportunities for more training for teachers regarding Inclusive Education is lacking.	3.34	Very Challenging
7. Teachers have no access to available indigenous teaching resources.	3.28	Very Challenging
8. A strong relationship with the Indigenous community in our locality is lacking	2.98	Moderately Challenging
9. There is no adequate support from the parents and community that would improve the implementation of IP education in the school.	3.01	Moderately Challenging
10. Lack of means to participate in any professional development focused on IP education.	3.20	Moderately Challenging
11. Failure to recognize the challenges of IP teaching as having great effects in the cohort survival rate of our indigenous learners.	3.24	Moderately Challenging
12. Opportunities to participate in further discussions of focus groups regarding the implementation of IP education is lacking.	3.26	Very Challenging
13. There is no sufficient time in student engagement especially to accommodate IP learners	3.14	Moderately Challenging
14. There are classroom management issues in the implementation of inclusive education.	3.04	Moderately Challenging
15. There is lack of support from IP parents in monitoring the attendance and progress of their children.	3.23	Moderately Challenging
TOTAL	3.19	Moderately Challenging

Table 27 discloses that lack of training on IP, inadequate resources (texts, materials, etc.), lack of opportunities for more training for teachers regarding Inclusive Education, no access to available indigenous teaching resources are very challenging for teachers. They are moderately challenged by no adequate support from the parents and

community that would improve the implementation of IP education in the school, and lack of a strong relationship with the Indigenous community in their locality. Overall, the teachers claim that that they are moderately challenged teaching the IP learners.

Based on the profile of the teachers, the majority are non-IPs, which means that there is a gap considering that majority of the learners are IPs. Thus, training really matters. When asked, teachers disclosed that they find difficulties dealing with the IP learners especially if they cannot understand the language of the learners. Imparting the lesson is challenging because at times, misinterpretation arises which is caused by language barriers. Another reason also is the culture of the IPs. There are some practices employed by the teachers which the learners cannot comprehend.

Accordingly, Learning Matters (2025) stated that teacher training is more critical now than ever because teachers today are struggling with identifying and filling the learning gaps in students to bring them up to grade level. In addition, they need to complete the current year's lesson plan as well. If there were ever a mammoth task, it is this. Without the right knowledge, tools, and skills, teachers cannot be expected to navigate these challenges on their own. When teachers attend training programs, it gives them the opportunity for continuous professional development - to learn new ways, methods, strategies, skills, and tools. When teachers get upskilled, they automatically feel confident, happy, and motivated to achieve greater things with their students. Confident and happy teachers mean confident and happy students.

c. **Students**

Table 28
Challenges Experienced by Students in Mainstream Education

Challenges	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The content standard in the different lessons is not relevant and useful to my daily life.	3.18	Moderately Challenging
2. The learning competencies being taught in the different subject areas are difficult to understand.	3.08	Moderately Challenging
3. The curriculum design does not include examples that reflect my culture and community.	2.94	Moderately Challenging
4. The literature we study does not include stories and authors that represent my culture.	2.95	Moderately Challenging
5. The language curriculum does not help me develop communication skills that will benefit me in my community.	3.02	Moderately Challenging
6. The curriculum does not include information pertinent to the traditional environmental practices of my community.	3.01	Moderately Challenging
7. I cannot see the connection between what we learn in the different subject areas and my community's way of life.	3.05	Moderately Challenging
8. The context taught in different subject areas does not accurately reflect the history and culture of my people.	2.98	Moderately Challenging
9. The curriculum lacks important discussions about Indigenous rights and contributions.	3.11	Moderately Challenging
10. The curriculum does not support the teachers' and students' cultural identity.	3.06	Moderately Challenging

11. There is no opportunity to suggest improvements to make the context more relevant to Indigenous issues.	3.04	Moderately Challenging
TOTAL	3.04	Moderately Challenging

Table 28 reveals the challenges encountered by the students. Data shows that they are moderately challenged by the curriculum design which does not include examples that reflect culture and community and the literature studied does not include stories and authors that represent their culture.

Students also are moderately challenged by the content standard in the different lessons which is not relevant and useful to their daily life and the curriculum lacks important discussions about Indigenous rights and contributions.

This implies that the students are challenged by the application of the lessons in daily life activities and the need for the inclusion of IPs rights and contribution in the subject matter. This connotes further that students tend to need more reality in the subject matter which they could interrelate it in their daily life experiences and in a way will also affect their right as IPs. Students reveal that there are lessons which are not applicable to their real situations, contextualizing lessons everyday leads teachers to focus more on lesson planning and searching for right terms for IPs.

Ferlazzo (2020) stated that one keyway to encourage intrinsic motivation to learn is by making classroom lessons relevant to students' lives. One of the struggles that teachers have when developing a lesson is thinking about: How will the lesson be relevant to students? How will students engage in the class in a way they feel is relevant to what they live on a day-to-day basis? By building relationships with students, teachers can motivate and understand the background of each student. Developing relationships with students provides teachers the opportunity to motivate students to use their capabilities and direct them in a path that can give them a successful outcome in school and in life.

By making lessons more relevant to students' lives and experiences, you can engage and help them: celebrate culture and have students teach others about their culture, allow students to share their stories and value their experiences: Students need a voice, lowering anxiety levels and giving students structured time to speak about who they are gives them the space to be heard and gives teachers the opportunity to build relationships with them and get to know who they are. Writing assignments can give us a clear view about who our students are, their interests, and their life experiences.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the practices employed and the challenges experienced by the respondents in mainstream education?

Table 29
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Practices of Teachers on Mainstream Education and the Challenges Experienced by the Administrators, Teachers, and Students

Variables	r- value	p – value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Practices of teachers as perceived by the administrators and challenges of Administrators	0.138	0.610	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Practices of teachers as perceived by the teachers themselves and The Challenges of Teachers	0.375	0.168	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Practices of teachers as perceived by the students and the Challenges of Students	0.129	0.705	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Table 29 presents the results of the tests of significant relationships between the perceived practices of teachers on mainstream education and the challenges experienced by the administrators, teachers, and students using the Pearson r-test at 0.05 level of significance.

The table reveals that the practices of teachers as perceived by administrators and the challenges experienced by administrators in mainstream education have a very weak positive linear relationship ($r = 0.138$), and the result is not significant ($p = 0.610$). This suggests that administrators' challenges are likely influenced by broader institutional or systemic concerns, rather than the extent to which they perceive teachers to be implementing mainstream education practices.

On the other hand, the teachers' practices on mainstream education as perceived by them and the challenges they encountered have an r -value of 0.375, indicating a moderate positive relationship. This implies that teachers who report higher levels of practice also tend to experience slightly more challenges. However, this relationship is not significant ($p = 0.168$), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Meanwhile, the practices of teachers in mainstream education as perceived by students and the challenges experienced by students yielded an r -value of 0.129, also reflecting a very weak correlation, and the p -value of 0.705 confirms that this relationship is not significant. This implies that students' perceived challenges are not significantly associated with how they perceive their teachers' implementation of mainstream

education. Their challenges may instead be shaped by personal, social, or instructional factors unrelated to teacher practices.

Conclusions

Teachers play a vital role in the successful implementation of mainstreaming in education. Their practices in relation to Curriculum Design, Competency and Content, Teaching Methodology and Strategies, Learning Space and Environment, Teaching Resources and Classroom Assessment demonstrate a strong commitment to meeting the diverse needs of indigenous students. The study shows that teachers strive to create inclusive environments where students with varying abilities can participate meaningfully with their other students.

However, despite the dedication, teachers encounter significant challenges in implementing mainstream effectively. These challenges often include limited training on inclusive strategies, insufficient resources and support services, lack of training and inadequate resources (texts, materials, etc.) that affect the teaching learning process of IP education effectively, no access to available indigenous teaching resources and lack of opportunities to participate in further discussions of focus groups regarding the implementation of IP education .

Finally, while teachers show willingness and professionalism in embracing mainstreaming practices, sustained success requires stronger institutional support, on going professional development, access to appropriate materials and collaborative partnership. Addressing these challenges will not only enhance teachers' effectiveness but also ensure that inclusive education fulfills its goals of equitable and quality learning opportunities for all students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion fo the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The Department of Education should design and implement more professional training regarding inclusive education to properly address the needs of the administrators, teachers and IP Learners.
2. Policy Makers should craft policies to further strengthen existing laws about the rights and beliefs of Indigenous learners to ensure a more comfortable cultural environment for the Ips.
3. Local Government Units (LGU) should allot a budget for financial assistance and environmental support for the IP communities, especially the needs of IP learners such as learning resources, protection and safe learning areas.
4. School Administrators need to design more functional IP programs that will help the teachers in mainstream education.

5. Teachers need to attend more seminars and training related to IPs for better understanding of their role in mainstream education and how to face the different challenges in mainstream education.
6. The Indigenous People Community should actively engage in the school program and encourage open dialogue in school. They should strengthen collaboration with the school authorities.
7. IP Parents should attend parent orientation and seminars to properly handle the challenges experienced by their children in their academic endeavors.
8. Indigenous Learners should be encouraged to actively participate in class discussion and other activities in school.
9. Future Researchers should use this study as a foundation for further research focusing on mainstream education particularly the indigenous learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted in full compliance with ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Permission was obtained from the Schools Superintendent and Assistant Superintendent of the Division of Isabela, and approval letters were provided to school heads prior to data collection. Participation of administrators, teachers, and Indigenous students was voluntary, with informed consent secured from all respondents and, where applicable, from parents or guardians. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and responses were used solely for research purposes. Data collection procedures respected the cultural backgrounds and practices of Indigenous learners, ensuring that interactions were culturally sensitive and non-intrusive. The researcher also safeguarded the psychological well-being of participants by providing clear explanations about the study's objectives and allowing respondents to withdraw at any time. All ethical requirements stipulated by institutional policies and Philippine regulations on research involving human subjects were adhered to throughout the study.

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REFERENCES

- Akintayo, O. T., Eden, C. A., Ayeni, O. O., & Onyebuchi, N. (2024). Inclusive curriculum design: Meeting the diverse needs of students for social improvement. *International Journal of Frontiers in Science and Technology Research*, 6(2), 50–59. <https://doi.org/10.53294/ijfstr.2024.6.2.0037>
- Alangui, W. V. (2024). Formulating an Indigenous curriculum framework for Indigenous Peoples' education in the Philippines
- Basiwal-Ao-wat, M., & Tovera-Ayang-ang, C. (2024). Roles of Indigenous peoples leaders in the indigenization of education: Basis for an Indigenous Peoples Education. *VOLUME 22, NO. 1, 1–[page range]*.
- Buenafior, N. B. R., Adiaton, J. G., Ancheta, G. J. C., Balading, J., Bravo, A. K. B., & Tu, J. (2023). The lived experiences and challenges faced by Indigenous high school students amidst the new normal of education. *A Multidisciplinary Journal Psychology and Education*, 7, 160–165. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7652948>
- Coral Care. (2025). Home page. Retrieved from <https://www.joincoralcare.com>
- DaiKiYa. (2024, June 21). DPsy – Lecture 10 – Middle adulthood – Student [PDF]. Scribd. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/document/743994941/DPsy-Lecture-10-Middle-adulthood-Student>
- Ferlazzo, L. (2020, May 26). Ways to make lessons 'relevant' to students' lives. *Education Week*. Retrieved from <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/opinion-ways-to-make-lessons-relevant-to-students-lives/2020/05>

- Langelaan, B. N., Gaikhorst, L., Smets, W., & Oostdam, R. J. (2024). Differentiating instruction: Understanding the key elements for successful teacher preparation and development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 140, 104464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104464>
- Learning Matters. (2025). The importance of teacher training programs. Retrieved from <https://learningmatters.ai/blog/the-importance-of-teacher-training-programs>
- Munna, A. S., & Kalam, A. (2021). Teaching and learning process to enhance teaching effectiveness: A literature review. *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI)*, 4(1), 1–4.
- Murray, S. (2024, July 8). Redefining male leadership: 8 essential qualities for success. Stu Murray. Retrieved from <https://www.stumurray.com/blog/embracing-the-full-spectrum-of-male-leadership-a-new-paradigm>
- Onyishi, N., & Sefotho, M. M. (2020). Teachers' perspectives on the use of differentiated instruction in inclusive classrooms: Implication for teacher education charity. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(6), 1–[page range].
- Schwartz, S. (2023, July 26). Teacher professional development, explained. Education Week. Retrieved from <https://www.edweek.org/leadership/teacher-professional-development-explained/2023/07>
- Sirisilla, S. (2023). Research methodology: Descriptive research design definition [Methodology description]. Studocu. Retrieved from <https://cdn2.f-cdn.com/files/download/208300149/FULL-BLOWN%20RESEARCH%20PAPER%20FOR%20MAED%20EDUC%20MANAGEMENT%20CLIENT.pdf>
- Tcheimegni, E. (2018). Including students with special needs in a mainstream classroom in Cameroon. [PDF].
- UNESCO International Bureau of Education. (2009). Policy guidelines on inclusion in education (Policy Guidelines for Inclusion in Education). UNESCO.
- United Nations (2009, August 31). Report of the Special Rapporteur on the right to education, Vernor Muñoz Villalobos: Addendum — Mission to Nepal (A/HRC/12/33/Add.1). United Nations. Retrieved from <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/G09/152/28/PDF/G0915228.pdf?OpenElement>
- Verdida, V. A., Malon, C., & Macalisang, D. (2024). Lived experiences of Indigenous people's education (IPED) in integrating the IPED curriculum. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(7), 455–466. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0193>